

Event Abstract

The Prevalence of Allergic Rhinitis in Libyan Asthmatic Patients

Ola Ezigllai, Hisham Alrabty*

Department of pediatrics, Tripoli children hospital, Tripoli, Libya.

Background: Allergic rhinitis is common association to asthma according to previous literature. Earlier studies showed that the control of allergic rhinitis improves overall asthma symptoms.

Objectives: The aim of the current study is to assess the prevalence of allergic rhinitis in Libyan asthmatic children who were attending regular follow up in asthma clinic of Tripoli children hospital during the year of 2008.

Methods: Data were collected by asking a total of 200 children's parents using pre-tested validated questionnaire composed of directly answered questions (yes or no) regarding the presence of symptoms such as rhinorrhea, nasal itching, and sneezing especially sessional symptoms.

Results: Our results exhibited that the incidence of allergic rhinitis in asthmatic Libyan children was 36.6%.

Conclusion: The obtained results revealed that allergic rhinitis is common and needs to be put in consideration in any asthma patient and treated accordingly.

Keywords: Asthma, allergic rhinitis, family history, association.

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* **Correspondence:** Dr. Hisham Alrabty, Department of pediatrics, Tripoli children hospital, Tripoli, Libya, arrabiti@hotmail.com